

BUILDING & SUSTAINING COMMUNITY PARTNERSHIPS

Who? Audience: Healthcare Organizations, Advocacy Groups, Research Institutions

Why? Long-Term Partnerships Matter

Sustainable partnerships create lasting impact, ensuring that engagement is not transactional but transformative.

How? Key Elements of Strong Partnerships

Reciprocity

Partnerships should benefit both the community and the organization.

Shared Leadership

Community partners should have a seat at decision-making tables.

Transparency

Clearly define roles, expectations, and long-term commitments.

Best Practices for Establishing Partnerships

Co-Design Programs

Work with—not for—communities to shape initiatives.

Invest in Relationship-Building

Engage outside of project cycles to foster trust.

Compensate Community Partners

Value their expertise and time.

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- **Chapter 2:** [Strengthening Partnerships to Reach Communities](#)
- **Chapter 5:** [Best Practices for Conducting Community Engaged Research](#)
- **Chapter 9:** [Positioned for Sustainability](#)

ACTION STEPS

- Identify shared goals and co-create initiatives
- Develop a memorandum of understanding (MOU) outlining partnership terms.
- Build feedback loops to refine and improve collaboration